

Hello!

Thank you for participating in the evaluation of **uvlhub.io** for publication in the Special Issue of the Journal of Systems and Software (JSS) on "Open science in Software Engineering research" with the title "UVLHub: a feature model data repository using UVL and open science principles".

uvlhub.io is a repository of feature models dataset in UVL format that follows Open Science principles. We would like to work with you to evaluate its usefulness and to improve the tool as much as possible. All model datasets uploaded to **uvlhub.io** are automatically uploaded to Zenodo. Don't worry, this is a development version, we are using the sandbox mode of Zenodo. Your data will not be visible in Zenodo in any way.

The estimated time for this evaluation is **20 minutes**. This evaluation is designed to be carried out with a laptop computer. Please ask us any questions you may have. This evaluation is anonymous and you do not need to identify yourself.

Thank you!

1. Preparation

You can download UVL models dataset from this link: <https://bit.ly/uvlhubdataset> . Use the following password: **uvlhub4ever**

dev.uvlhub.io/signup

2. Tasks realization

The following are some of the tasks you should try to perform.

PLEASE, indicate the start date and time of this evaluation: _____

#	Task description	Time and minute of completion (hh:mm)	metrics		
			Task completed? (YES / NO)	Assisted task (YES / NO)	Any incidents during the performance of this task? (YES / NO)
1	Create an account in https://dev.uvlhub.io/signup/				
2	Upload a dataset of 2-3 model				
2.1	Check that when you upload a UVL file, its upload is validated and if it is syntactically valid with a visual tick.				
2.2	Check that you can only upload files in UVL format				
2.3	Check that you can add or remove authors				
2.4	Check that you can add relevant metadata to each model independently.				
3	Retrieve the files (download) from the one you have just uploaded.				
4	Check that your dataset has an associated unique identifier (DOI).				
5	Using the search engine, search for your dataset by author name.				
6	Using the search engine, search for a dataset related to an online shop.				

If you have experienced any problems while performing a task, please indicate them:

3. Satisfaction survey

Mark with an X for each question, where **1 = strongly disagree** and **5 = strongly agree**.

		1	2	3	4	5
1	<i>I need to learn many concepts before I can use uvlhub.io effectively.</i>					
2	<i>uvlhub.io met all my needs in terms of functionality.</i>					
3	<i>The information provided by uvlhub.io was irrelevant to my tasks.</i>					
4	<i>I was able to complete my tasks efficiently using uvlhub.io</i>					
5	<i>I can't find an easy way to access the models.</i>					
6	<i>I find the metrics that accompany the models useful.</i>					
7	<i>I consider that uvlhub.io does not add value to my work or study.</i>					
8	<i>Finding a model that met my needs was relatively easy.</i>					
9	<i>I think that the way of organizing the models by means of datasets is not the correct one.</i>					
10	<i>I would recommend uvlhub.io to others based on its usefulness.</i>					

4. Free text

Please feel free to express your opinion.

I criticize...

I applaud...

I propose...

Thank you very much for participating in the
uvlhub.io evaluation!

